

THE ESP MANUAL: PRINCIPLES OF CREATING, DESIGNING STUDY MATERIALS WITH TRANSLATION

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Abstract:

This is a research on teaching English for Specific Purposes to adult learners. Analysis of available ESP course books, manuals goals and outcomes of ESP teaching, the effective structure of ESP manuals, materials selection for course book, activities used to teach ESP teaching, translation etc. are viewed in the article.

Key words: manual, creation, cognitive requirements, sequencing of course content, exhibit the project, implementation.

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Manual evaluation is a process of selecting what textbook to use by considering the need and value of teaching and learning. It is essential for teachers since it provides useful information for planning and managing activities or tasks by learners in classroom practice. A significant number of ESP research papers, books and course books (or manuals) have been already developed, for different levels and professional branches, within the framework of applied linguistics and ELT (FLT). The objective of the current article will not be though to summarize essential works in this field, but based on distinguished cognitive and applied linguists' studies, ESP course books and on author's research, to consider issues related to the ESP manual and study materials design with respect to cognitive teaching requirements and display leaning strategies exemplification across course books. [1, p 3]

The paper layout will be the following. Firstly, the cognitive ESP curriculum, underlying the creation of the cognitive ESP manual and study materials will be presented in terms of its general characteristics and advantages. The ESP manual preparation stages, also applicable to study materials design steps, will be mentioned; next, selection, grading and creation of study materials will be treated, emphasis being put on cognitively based activities; exemplifying instances of cognitive activities aimed at language awareness (LA) improvement within skills teaching will be provided. Illustrations will be founded on excerpts from ESP course books in engineering. Conclusions will be finally made as to the efficiency of cognitively designed ESP manuals with respect to skills, knowledge and motivation parameters enhancement.

Language content and exercises - Regarding language content and exercises, Harding (2007) suggests that ESP teachers should use contexts, texts and situations from the students' subject area. Whether they are simulated or real, they will involve naturally the language that the students need. Further, he adds that they should exploit authentic materials that students use in their vocation or specialism – and don't be put off by this idea that it may not seem "normal English". According to him, ESP teachers should make the tasks authentic and get students doing things with the material that they actually need to do in their work. Additionally, Skierso (1991) suggests some criteria for the evaluation of exercises. He wonders whether there is a variety of activities in the textbook, and whether the instructions to the activities are appropriate for the level of students.

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Skills and strategies - McDonough and Shaw (2003) stated that materials should enable the learners to see how the four skills (listening, speaking, reading, and writing) can be used effectively in appropriate contexts. According to them, as integrated skills materials are likely to involve learners in authentic and realistic tasks, their motivation level will increase. So, they perceive a clear rationale behind what they are being asked to do. Hyland (2005) states that specialist' samples, despite the fact that these samples are useful, may discourage students if the contents of these samples are too difficult (cited in McDonough, 2005). According to Belcher (2006), both tasks and authentic texts are advocated strongly in ESP material design.

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A few studies have been conducted on the textbook evaluation. It seems that there is a shortage of study with respect to ESP textbook of computer engineering major. Thus, it remains a challenge to select an appropriate ESP textbook in this case. Since this is the first study that is focused on the ESP textbook of computer engineering major taught at Payame Noor Universities in Iran, the obtained results may be beneficial for the ESP teachers and material developers.

A few studies have been conducted on the textbook evaluation. It seems that there is a shortage of study with respect to ESP textbook of different subjects and topics. Thus, it remains a challenge to select an appropriate ESP textbook in this case. Since this is the first study that is focused on the ESP manuals Biology and the history of Uzbekistan taught at Navoi state pedagogical institute, the obtained results may be beneficial for the ESP teachers and material developers.

Before creating course manual, students are given some specific features of designing manuals. Some general rules of design will be helpful, when creating and designing a textbook. Begin with the end in mind. What is it that you are trying to achieve? Sketch out the general parameters of your book. What types of media do you want to incorporate to your book? Make a plan for the future. Who will review your book? How to work with the words and word combinations in translation?

Master degree students of our Institution are required to make course manuals related to their personal interest and attempt. Course structure refers to the choice of topics, organization, and sequencing of course content. The choice of topics and their organization should always support the learning objectives for the course. In some cases, illustrators or photographers also contribute to the design of book covers. Course manual design matters because it can make or break student engagement—and, ultimately, student success. Primarily, always start with the end in mind. We want my students to achieve specific learning objectives by the end of the course.

Before you start creating the actual content of your book, it is strongly recommended that you do some market research. Discuss your project with others to find out what teachers and ESP language learners want. Start by making a list of all the concepts you want to cover. Then think about how they will fit together to form the different chapters. Chapters be independent of each other, a textbook should be organized logically. Only then will you convey your knowledge correctly to the students. Pay particular attention to the title (headings and subheadings), and do not hesitate to insert boxes throughout the manual. Summary sheets at the end of the manual are also a good idea. The students design the manual cover, table of contents, acknowledgement, reference, and the book template of compiled unit from units from unit 1 until 10. In the final process, the students will result on one course book of ESP for particular field, in the form of hard and soft copy. Translating a text for a manual, which aims to inform or persuade, is not the same as translating a text that is going to be posted on social media and is designed to entertain, be funny or cause a reaction, or a blog post, which intends to be informative. What's more, something that is funny in one culture may not be in another.

Project based learning in teaching learning process, such as:

1. Get an idea. The outcome of a project might be a product (such as a machine or an artwork), a performance (such as a theatre piece or a debate), or a service (such as giving a lesson to younger students) that the outcome be something that students (as well as other people) value. Other important point in getting the idea is the projects will be able to help students to master the content that they are required to learn and the students can learn something meaningful from the projects.

2. Design the project. Backwards planning is a very simple way of working. To begin, the teachers write down everything that they expect their students to learn from doing this project. This could include all kinds of things: knowledge of course-specific content, generic skills like working in teams and analyzing drafts, specialist skills (which could range from statistical analysis to carving wood), and personal attributes such as self-confidence. It is important to prepare project plan template for the students to ensure that they do not forget about anything important.

3. Tune the project. This means presenting the plans to a group of colleagues, who will give constructive feedback, come up with ideas that have not thought of and warn the potential problems that may not have anticipated.

4. Do the project. There are many ways to begin a project: one is to start by giving the students space to talk about what they are concerned about and interested in, and then talking about how the project can speak to these concerns and interests.

5. Translation process. Translation also plays a pivotal role in cultural exchange. It allows us to experience foreign art, music, and films, broadening our access to different cultural expressions. This exchange of ideas fosters empathy, breaks down stereotypes, and promotes respect among nations and communities

6. Exhibit the project. This step allows the students to promote their project go public. There are many possible venues for exhibitions: museums, galleries, parks, cafes, community centers, auditorium etc.

Students must consider four primary elements when designing their manuals learning outcomes, assessments, teaching and learning activities, and content. Language learners should follow three models of curriculum design: subject-centered, learner-centered, and problem-centered design.

The Distribution of the Tasks on project work are given: Creating and designing a course manual on the theme: Politics and politicians in the world, Economy and business, Culture and Sport, Migration and globalization, Climate and Environmental Psychology, Youth and opportunity, English as international language, English for 21st century skills. ICT in language teaching, English for Tourism and hospitality marketing, Medicine and medical supplies, Psychological factors in language learning, Banking and financial services.

Table 2. Detail Projects of ESP Course

Time	Task	Detail
Month: October	Doing need analysis.	The students were asked to interview/ observe/give questionnaire to other students in other study program like <i>economy, mathematics</i> , etc., in order to get the information of the students' need towards English. The result of the interview/observation/ questionnaire were analyzed to know the need of the students.
Month: November	Designing Syllabus	The syllabus were designed based on the results of need analysis. The syllabus was made in a simple form, which consist of language focus and content focus. Every class produced one syllabus with 10 sub materials, which would be developed further into teaching materials.
Month: December	Designing Course book	The syllabus was developed into materials of ESP. The course books should cover language skills, vocabularies, and grammatical features. The materials of one field of study are divided into 10 units, in which every unit was designed by each group.
Month: January	Final Process	The students designs the book cover, table of content, acknowledgement, reference, and the book template of compiled unit from units from unit 1 until 10. In the final process, the students will result on one course book of ESP for particular field, in the form of hard and soft copy.

Conclusion. Specifically, in teaching English for Specific Purposes (ESP), textbooks play a significant role in enhancing students' learning of specialized English skills and using such skills to address occupational needs. Thus, the use of cognitive study materials corroborates learner motivation and, consequently, promotes independent studying, self-assessment and learner responsibility.

Analyzing and using some ESP textbooks and manuals in teaching process, we, as teachers have realized that the textbook, manuals provide some examples to support the activities, important proved factors, essential topics and vocabulary to study and translate. Additionally, the sequencing of content on the basis of complexity and the suitability of topics are not different from what students expected. The students' responses on the questionnaire items imply the need for paying attention to weaknesses. Besides, encouraging students to become independent learners has been overlooked.

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